

MECHANICAL PROPERTY OF CARBON NANOTUBE YARN REINFORCED EPOXY

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1 Introduction

Carbon fibers, which have high specific strength and stiffness, are the main stream of reinforcement of composites used for light-weight structural components. Carbon nanotubes (CNT) are anticipated to exceed the mechanical properties of carbon fibers. Growing continuous CNT, however, has limitation so far, and thus it is difficult to use CNT as structural components. In order to resolve the problem, spinning of CNTs have been investigated [1-2]. However, the basic mechanical properties of CNT spun yarn and its composite have not been clarified yet.

In this study, tensile tests of CNT spun yarn reinforced composite were conducted and mechanical properties were obtained to investigate the mechanical behavior of CNT spun yarn reinforced composite.

2 Materials

Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWNTs) used in this study were grown on a quartz glass plate with chemical vapor deposition using C₂H₂ and FeCl₂ as a base material and a catalyst, respectively [3]. MWNTs on a substrate look like a head of a tooth brush, and thus called a MWNT array. Figure 1 shows a MWNT array. MWNTs are contracted by Van der Waals' force during drawing process from a CNT array. Figure 2 shows a schematic and photograph of drawing a MWNT spun yarn. The MWNT length was about 1 mm and the diameter was about 50 nm. Figure 3 shows a SEM image of a spun yarn. The yarn diameter was about 45 μm. The twist angle is defined as the angle between the yarn axis and the outermost fiber direction.

Room temperature cured epoxy (Bisphenol-A type, Nisshin Resin Z2/H07) was used for composite specimens.

Fig.1 MWNT array

(a) Schematic of drawing a spun yarn

(b) Drawing of a spun yarn

Fig.2. Drawing of MWNT spun yarn

Fig.3. SEM image of a spun yarn

3 Tensile Test of MWNT Spun Yarn

Specimens for tensile tests were prepared as shown in Fig.4. The both ends of spun yarn were glued onto a paper mount with a slight tensile force. The gauge length was 15mm. After the specimen was gripped, the paper mount was cut and tensile tests were conducted at 1mm/min of the cross head speed. Displacement was measured by a noncontact extensometer. Figure 5 shows typical stress–strain curves of tensile tests. Each lot showed different stress–strain behavior because the twist angle had strong influence on it.

A yarn with $\alpha=21^\circ$ had high strength but small elongation, whereas a yarn with $\alpha=40^\circ$ had low strength but large elongation. A yarn with $\alpha=30^\circ$ showed intermediate behavior between with $\alpha=21^\circ$ and 40° .

Figure 6 shows the variations of Young's modulus and tensile strength with twist angle. Young's modulus was defined in the range of $\varepsilon = 0.25\text{--}0.5\%$. They strongly depended on the twist angle. They had the maximum values around $20^\circ\text{--}25^\circ$. Higher angle of MWNT spun yarn caused lower strength and Young's modulus.

Fig.4. Tensile specimen of MWNT spun yarn.

Fig.5. Typical stress-strain curves of MWNT spun yarn.

(a) Young's modulus

(b) Tensile strength

Fig.6. Effect of twist angle on mechanical properties.

Figure 7 shows SEM images of fracture portions of MWNT spun yarns. Similar fracture morphology was observed for each specimen. In the fracture portion, pullouts of MWNT fibers and fiber bundles were observed.

(a) $\alpha=17^\circ$

(b) $\alpha=21^\circ$

(c) $\alpha=29^\circ$

(d) $\alpha=39^\circ$

Fig.7. SEM image of fracture portion of MWNT spun yarn.

Figure 8 shows a typical cyclic stress–strain curve of spun yarns, where the maximum load for each cycle was increased incrementally. Nonlinearity and hysteresis were clearly observed.

These results imply that slippage among MWNT fibers is probably the reason of the tensile fracture.

Fig.8. Typical cyclic stress–strain curve.

4 Fabrication of MWNT Yarn Reinforced Epoxy
Composite specimens using MWNT spun yarns were fabricated by using a pultrusion technique with seven yarns as shown in Fig.9. The epoxy matrix was cured at room temperature for 72 hour. The tensile load was controlled by changing the dead weight from 10–30g. Figure 10 was an optical micro scope image of the composite cross section.

The fiber volume fraction was estimated using the following expression.

$$V_f = \frac{V_{MWNT}}{V_{comp}} = \frac{A_{yarn}}{A_{comp}} \cdot \frac{\rho_{yarn}}{\rho_{MWNT}} \quad (1)$$

where A_{yarn} is the density of yarn, A_{comp} is the density of MWNT, ρ_{yarn} is the density of yarn, and ρ_{MWNT} is the density of MWNT. ρ_{MWNT} is assumed to be 2.1 g/cm³. The fiber volume fractions of MWNT spun yarn were about 19.7–25.5%. Figure 11 shows the relationship between the dead weight and fiber volume fraction. It is found that applying tensile load during cure is an effective way of increasing the fiber volume fraction.

Fig.9. Fabrication of composite specimen.

Fig.10. Optical microscopic image of cross section of MWNT spun yarn.

Fig.11. Fiber volume fraction vs. Dead weight during cure

5 Tensile Test of MWNT Yarn Reinforced Epoxy

The specimen shape and tensile test conditions were the same as those for spun yarns. Figure 12 shows the typical stress–strain curves of epoxy composites fabricated by using a pultrusion technique. The stress–strain curves of the composite were almost linear whereas those of spun yarn were nonlinear as shown in Fig.5. Note that the tensile modulus and strength of composites are higher than those of yarn. The maximum tensile strength and Young’s modulus were 485MPa and 53GPa, respectively. The maximum tensile strength was about 6 times as high as the resin strength, and Young’s modulus was about 20 times as high as the resin modulus.

Fig.12. Typical stress–strain curves of MWNT spun yarn reinforced composites.

Young's modulus and tensile strength are plotted as a function of the fiber volume fraction in Fig. 13 and Fig.14. The increase in fiber volume fraction resulted in the increase in the Young's modulus and tensile strength, though the linear regressions in Fig. 13 and 14 seemed not to be appropriate. The deviation from the linear regression was contributed by the fiber angle change caused by tensile load during cure.

Figure 15 shows the relationship between the stiffness (i.e. spring constant) of composites and the dead weight, and Fig. 16 shows the relationship between the fracture load and the dead weight. Remember that the number of yarns used for composite specimens was unchanged. Thus Figs. 15 and 16 means that the dead weight contributed to change the fiber angle toward the fiber axis as well as to increase the fiber volume fraction.

Fig.13. Young's modulus vs. Fiber volume fraction.

Fig.14. Tensile strength vs. Fiber volume fraction.

Fig.15. Spring constant vs. Dead weight

Fig.16. Fracture load vs. Dead weight

(a) $V_f=19.7\%$

(b) $V_f=20.0\%$

(c) $V_f=23.9\%$

(d) $V_f=25.5\%$

Fig.17. Fracture surface

(a) $V_f=19.7\%$

(b) $V_f=20.0\%$

(c) $V_f=23.9\%$

(d) $V_f=25.5\%$

Fig.18. Magnified view of fracture surface

(a) $V_f = 19.7\%$

(a) $V_f = 19.7\%$

(b) $V_f = 20.0\%$

(b) $V_f = 20.0\%$

(c) $V_f = 23.9\%$

(c) $V_f = 23.9\%$

(d) $V_f = 25.5\%$

Fig.19. Fracture portion

(d) $V_f = 25.5\%$

Fig.20. Magnified view of fracture portion

Figures 17 and 18 show the fracture surface, and Figures 19 and 20 show the side view of the fracture surface. Fracture surfaces were almost flat and the pull-out length was about 10 μm . Since the fiber length was about 1 mm or longer, the fracture mode was probably fiber breakage.

4. Conclusions

Tensile tests of MWNT spun yarn and MWNT composite were conducted. As a result, it was found that tensile strength and Young's modulus of spun yarn were influenced by twist angle. Tensile strength and Young's modulus of spun yarn showed maximum values around 20°. Fracture of MWNT spun yarn is probably dominated by slippage among MWNTs. MWNT spun yarn reinforcement effectively enhanced the mechanical properties of epoxy. Average strength was about 6 times as high as the resin strength, and Young's modulus was about 20 times as high as the resin modulus.

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